

Application of SAK EMKM to MSME Business Actors

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ABSTRACT

Micro, small and medium enterprises in the city of Palopo are still constrained by the application of financial accounting standards for micro, small and medium entities. If left unchecked, it will complicate the preparation of financial reports. This study aims to identify and analyze the factors that influence the application of SAK EMKM to MSME business actors in Palopo City. The population and sample for this study were 90 micro, small and medium business actors who met the sample criteria. This type of research data uses primary data in the form of a questionnaire. Data analysis uses multiple linear regression analysis using Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS). The results of the study show that socialization, education level, perceptions and understanding of accounting have a significant and significant effect on the application of SAK EMKM.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of economic development is a concept of community empowerment that is sustainable, empowering and person-centred. To develop and support the community, the concept of economic development is an effort to empower the community involving micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) carried out by the government (Sugiyarsih, 2019). MSMEs are a place for job creation and good economic growth. MSMEs play a very important role in the Indonesian economy which produces output that is useful for society and contributes to economic development in Indonesia (Hasan et al., 2022).

In research conducted by Kusuma & Lutfiany (2019) stated that one form of business that is able to save the national economy and will survive to this day compared to other business sectors is MSME. In addition, MSMEs also play a role in absorbing labor and driving the pace of economic growth and driving the production business sector in various business fields (Susilowati et al., 2021). However, until now one of the obstacles that often occurs and is faced by business actors, namely limitations in recording and preparing financial reports. To reflect the business activities carried out by MSME actors, financial reports are required for 1 period. To meet the information needs of MSMEs actors, therefore in 2009 the Indonesian Accounting Association as a professional organization as well as the setting body for financial accounting standards (SAK) through the DSAK IAI or the Financial Accounting Standards Board of the Indonesian Accounting Association compiled and ratified IFRS for SMEs (international financial reporting). Standard for small medium enterprises) (Kusuma & Lutfiany, 2019).

IFRS for SMEs is a standard for accounting for financial entities without public accountability (SAK ETAP). But currently, the implementation of SAK ETAP has not been maximized by MSME business actors. This is caused by a lack of knowledge and lack of information which is the motivation for implementing reporting in accordance with accounting standards (Susilowati et al., 2021). Regarding MSME actors who have not implemented SAK ETAP optimally, so the organization IAI has prepared accounting standards that are in accordance with MSME financial reporting, namely micro, small and medium entity accounting standards (SAK EMKM) which were then ratified on October 24 2016 and in January 2018 have been in effect and used by business actors. It is hoped that with this SAK EMKM, in preparing the financial statements of small and medium companies, they will be able to use the standards that have been set (Kusuma & Lutfiany, 2019).

The concept of SAK EMKM is simpler and less complicated than SAK ETAP. In preparing and making SAK EMKM based on Law No. 20 of 2008 concerning MSMEs (Adino, 2019). With the implementation of SAK EMKM in Indonesia, it is hoped that it will be able to assist business actors in compiling financial reports accurately and precisely without getting caught up in the complexities of current financial accounting standards. SAK EMKM is an accounting standard used for MSME business actors which is much simpler than SAK ETAP, where SAK EMKM is shown for entities that are not or have not been able to meet the accounting requirements regulated by SAK STAP

(Syukrina & Janrosl, 2018). In preparing the SAK EMKM financial reports using the concept of business entities and the preparation using the basic assumptions of accruals and business continuity as used by micro, small and medium entities (Kusuma & Lutfiany, 2019).

The results of previous research also explain that in implementing SAK EMKM, not many MSMEs have implemented it. This can be seen from socialization factors, level of education, perception of actors and understanding of accounting regarding the implementation of SAK EMKM. In research conducted by Syukrina (2018) and Sutapa (2020), socialization influenced the implementation of SAK EMKM. In research conducted by Sutapa (2020), it was stated that the perceptions of MSME actors had no influence on the implementation of SAK EMKM. In research, Kusuma (2019) stated that the level of education influences the implementation of SAK EMKM. In contrast to research conducted by Syukrina (2018), the perceptions of MSME actors have a significant influence on the implementation of SAK EMKM. In research conducted by Neneng Salmiah, Satria Tri Nanda (2018) stated that understanding accounting influences the implementation of SAK EMKM.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Stewardship Theory

Stewardship theory is a framework which argues that a person works basically motivated because of the responsibilities assigned to them (Seftiany & Wijayana, 2023). This theory departs from a management accounting perspective based on sociological and psychological theories (Anton, 2010). Basically, stewardship theory states that in carrying out work, a person is more collectively oriented so that common goals can be realized (Seftiany & Wijayana, 2023). Organizational management in this theory focuses on harmonization between capital owners and capital managers so that goals are achieved together. In accounting, this theory explains a construct of communication relationships and leadership patterns between shareholders and management (Anton, 2010).

Socialization

In society, socialization, especially socialization related to SAK EMKM, is able to encourage the community's desire to immediately implement SAK EMKM (Susilowati et al., 2021). Socialization is identified with the meaning of adjustment (adjustment). In life, a series or teaching and learning process is seen as socialization (Syukrina & Janrosl, 2018). Good socialization can result in a person's process of acquiring skills, knowledge and attitudes. Socialization occurs through environmental conditions that cause individuals to learn fundamental cultural patterns (Susilowati et al., 2021). The newly approved SAK EMKM policy certainly requires socialization in its application to generate a good understanding and implementation of SAK EMKM (Sutapa, 2020). In Yunarti and Wahyuni's research (2017) socialization has a function as a role in a position or a role in a person's results in acquiring knowledge, skills and

attitudes. In research conducted by Sutapa (2020) it was stated that socialization had an influence on the implementation of SAK EMKM.

Level Education

In education, a person or group of people is in the process of changing attitudes and maturing thinking patterns through teaching and training efforts (Febriyanti & Wardhani, 2018). A company's performance in improving and increasing its competitiveness is influenced by the education level of the owner, manager or employee of a company. The level of education that the owner, employee or manager has taken in the company, both formal and non-formal education, determines ability and expertise (Adino, 2019). Education is a learning process for a group of people to gain knowledge, skills and habits through teaching, training or research to be passed on to the next generation (Febriyanti & Wardhani, 2018). According to Kusuma (2019), his research stated that the level of education influences the implementation of SAK EMKM.

Perception

Of course, each business owner has a different perception of the applicable financial accounting standards (Syukrina & Janrosl, 2018). In Yunari and Wahyuni's research (2017), perception is a person's attitude in seeing and interpreting every event, object or human. Perception can also be interpreted as vision, where the vision in question is how someone perceives or interprets something (Syukrina & Janrosl, 2018). Perception is a broad picture of someone about something related to selection, organizing and interpreting which has an overall meaning (Susilowati et al., 2021). In society, socialization, especially socialization related to SAK EMKM, is able to encourage the community's desire to immediately implement SAK EMKM (Susilowati et al., 2021). Socialization is identified with the meaning of adjustment. In life, a series or teaching and learning process is seen as socialization (Syukrina & Janrosl, 2018). Good socialization can result in a person's process of acquiring skills, knowledge and attitudes. The application of SAK EMKM is also influenced by the actors' perceptions and accounting understanding of the MSME actors themselves. In previous research conducted by Syukrina (2018) stated that perceptions affect the application of SAK EMKM.

Understanding accounting

Understanding accounting is a person's ability to understand and understand something (Susilowati et al., 2021). To know something, the concept of understanding can be seen from various ways aspects, for example when someone gives an explanation and interprets words using their own sentences. Understanding can also be interpreted as the ability to capture both the meaning and meaning of the material being studied (Kusuma & Lutfiany, 2019). In implementing understanding of accounting, financial statements are needed in accordance with SAK EMKM. The better the accounting understanding of MSME owners or business actors, the better their ability to apply SAK EMKM to financial reports (Mutuari & Yudiantara, 2021). According to Neneng Salmiah,

Satria Tri Nanda (2018) states that understanding accounting influences the application of SAK EMKM.

Based on the explanation above, the conceptual framework in this research is seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Based on the background and framework that has been described previously, the research hypothesis is as follows:

H1: Socialization has a positive and significant effect on SAK EMKM

H2: Education level has a positive and significant effect on SAK EMKM

H3: Perception has a positive and significant effect on SAK EMKM

H4: Understanding of accounting has a positive and significant effect on SAK EMKM

METHODOLOGY

The quantitative approach used in this research is primary data. In taking samples, this research used a questionnaire distributed to MSMEs in Palopo City. The research period begins in June 2022. This research uses a population of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) registered with the Department of Cooperatives and Micro Enterprises of Palopo City. The technique and method for collecting data is by surveying and distributing questionnaires to micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) using purposive sampling in taking samples that are in accordance with the criteria for business actors in the culinary and fashion business sectors.

This research uses multiple linear regression analysis using SPSS version 26 with data analysis using quantitative data with independent variables. Multiple linear regression measures measure the equation of the independent variable to the dependent variable or the independent variable and the dependent variable.

RESULTS

Overview of Respondents

The following (table 1) presents information regarding the general description of the demographic conditions of the respondents.

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics of Respondents	Amount	%
Age/Year		
≤ 20 Year	0	-
21-25 Year	18	16,2
26-30 Year	29	26,1
31-35 Year	30	27,0
36-40 Year	13	11,7
Total	90	100
Gender		
Woman	68	66,7
Man	22	33,3
Total	90	100
Last Education		
SD/MI	0	6,7
SMP/MTs	2	16,6
SMA/SMK/MA	46	66,7
D3	20	6,7
S1-S3	22	3,3
Total	90	100
Length of Business/Years		
≤ 1 Year	22	16,6
1-5 Year	46	66,8
6-10 Year	22	16,6
≥ 10 Year	0	-
Total	90	100

In this research, a general description of respondents was used in the survey based on age, gender, highest level of education and length of business. The table above shows that business actors are predominantly aged 31-35 years, namely 30 people or 27.0%. Furthermore, the female gender dominates with 68 people or 66.7% compared to male MSME actors. Furthermore, the last education of micro, small and medium business actors is more dominant with SMA/SMK/MA graduates with 46 people or 66.7% compared to SD, SMP, D3 and S1-S3 graduates. Furthermore, the length of time the business has been running is more dominant, 1-5 years, as many as 46 people or 66.8%.

Validity and Reliability Test

The following are the results of testing using SPSS 26, by testing the validity and reliability of the research variables as follows.

Tabel 2. Validity and Reliability Test

Variable	Item	r count	r table	Cronbach's Alpha	Description
Socialization	X1.1	0,665		0,758	Valid/Realibel
	X1.2	0,779			

	X1.3	0,497	0,2050			
	X1.4	0,730				
Level education	X2.1	0,751			0,739	Valid/Reliable
	X2.2	0,497				
	X2.3	0,519				
	X2.4	0,715				
Perception	X3.1	0,285			0,741	Valid/Reliable
	X3.2	0,819				
	X3.3	0,735				
	X4.4	0,666				
Understanding Accountry	X4.1	0,571			0,734	Valid/Reliable
	X4.2	0,683				
	X4.3	0,662				
	X4.4	0,573				
Application of SAK EMKM	Y1	0,693		0,681	Valid/Reliable	
	Y2	0,411				
	Y3	0,490				
	Y4	0,606				

Source: primary data processed (2022)

Based on table 2, all statement items on the socialization variable, education level, perception, understanding of accounting, and application of the EMKM SAK are declared valid because $r_{count} > r_{table}$ 0.2050. For the results of the reliability test of the socialization variable, education level, perception, understanding of accounting, and the application of the EMKM SAK it can be concluded that all statement items are reliable because the overall value of the Cronbach alpha variable is greater than 0.60.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is a statistical test of questions using the t statistical test, the coefficient of determination test (R²) and the simultaneous significance test (statistical F test). The t statistical test is a test that aims to determine the effect of significant independent variables on the dependent variable formulated in the model.

Table 3. Statistical Test t

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8.834	1.012		8.732	0.000
	Total X1	0.289	0.076	0.333	1.710	0.001
	Total X2	0.263	0.087	0.366	3.005	0.003
	Total X3	0.259	0.085	0.292	2.696	0.000
	Total X4	0.285	0.088	0.408	3.252	0.002

a. Dependent Variable: Total Y

Source: Output SPSS, 2022

The first hypothesis (H1) is known for socialization (X1) t count = 1.710 > t table = 1.662 with sig. 0.001 < 0.05 means that there is a positive and significant influence on the application of SAK EMKM. The second hypothesis (H2) is known for the level of education (X2) t count = 3.005 > t table = 1.662 with sig. 0.003 < 0.05 means that there is a positive and significant influence on the application of SAK EMKM. The third hypothesis (H3) is known for perception (X3) t count = 2.696 > t table = 1.662 with sig. 0.000 < 0.05 means that there is a positive and significant influence on the application of SAK EMKM. The fourth hypothesis (H4) is known for understanding accounting (X4) t count = 3.252 > t table = 1.662 with sig. 0.002 < 0.05 means that there is a positive and significant influence on the implementation of SAK EMKM.

The coefficient of determination test (R²) is a test of magnitude that shows a comparison of the variations in the independent variables that are able to explain the variations in the dependent variable. Seen in the following table, which shows the results of the coefficient of determination test (R²) as follows:

Table 4. Coefficient of Determination Test (R²)

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.635 ^a	0.404	0.376	1.531

Source: Output SPSS, 2022

Based on the table above, it is known that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.376 meaning that socialization, education level, perception and understanding of accounting have an influence of 37.6% on the application of SAK EMKM while 62.4% is influenced by other variables. The F statistical test can be seen by looking at the significant value of 0.05 and aiming for determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

Table 5. Statistical Test F

ANOVA ^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	134.959	4	33.740	14.392	.000 ^b
	Residual	199.263	85	2.344		
	Total	334.222	89			
a. Dependent Variable: Total Y						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Total X4, Total X2, Total X1, Total X3						

Source: Output SPSS, 2022

Judging from the significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and the calculated F value of $14.392 > F$ table 2.47 in the t statistical test, it can be concluded that in this research, all independent variables simultaneously influence the dependent variable. This study uses a multiple linear regression data analysis model. In multiple regression analysis the functional relationship of the dependent variable is influenced by two or more independent variables. From the multiple linear regression analysis test it can be seen in table 3 and a constant value of 8.834 is obtained and the coefficient value for variable X1 is 0.289, X2 is 0.263, X3 is 0.259 and X4 is 0.285, so the regression equation is obtained as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + e$$

$$Y = a + 0.289X_1 + 0.263X_2 + 0.259X_3 + 0.285X_4 + e$$

The results of the multiple regression equation are obtained as follows:

- a. The constant value of 8.834 has a positive value, which means that the socialization variable, education level, perception and understanding of accounting is zero (0), so the EMKM SAK implementation variable has increased by 8.834.
- b. The regression coefficient for the socialization variable (X1) has increased by 0.289, which means that if the other variables have a fixed value and have increased, then the SAK EMKM implementation variable (Y) has increased by 0.289 with the assumption that the level of education, perception and understanding of accounting is constant. From the results of the regression analysis, it can be seen that the influence of socialization is very small because it is only 0.289, so there are a lot of efforts we can make to provide understanding related to SAK EMKM. Socialization can be carried out using various sources such as print media, digital media as well as holding seminars or workshops on preparing SAK EMKM for MSME business actors.
- c. The regression coefficient of the education level variable (X2) has increased by 0.263, which means that if the other variables have a fixed value and have increased, then the variable applying SAK EMKM (Y) has increased by 0.263 with the assumption that socialization, perceptions and understanding of accounting are constant. From the results of the education level variable regression, It can be seen that the influence of this level of education is very small. We see that most of the MSME actors in the city of Palopo come from the last education of

SMA/SMK/MA, so there is a lack of knowledge related to the preparation of SAK EMKM.

- d. The regression coefficient for the perception variable (X3) has increased by 0.259, which means that if the other variables have a fixed value and have increased, then the variable implementing SAK EMKM (Y) has increased by 0.259 with the assumption that socialization, level of education and understanding of accounting are constant values. From the variable regression results, it shows that the influence of this perception is 0.259, meaning it has a very small influence.
- e. The regression coefficient for the accounting understanding variable (X4) has decreased by 0.285, which means that if the other variables have a fixed value and have decreased, then the variable implementing SAK EMKM (Y) has decreased by 0.285 with the assumption that socialization, education level and perception are constant values. From the results of the regression test it can be concluded that understanding accounting has a very small influence. This is because, in general, MSME business actors have graduated from SMA/SMK/MA, whereas we understand that understanding of accounting is obtained at college or attending courses, seminars and workshops. So that the implementation of financial reports is in accordance with applicable standards, MSME business actors have not felt and realized the benefits.

DISCUSSION

Socialization Affects the Application of SAK EMKM

Based on the first hypothesis shows that the socialization variable shows a positive value It can be seen that the influence of this level of education is very small. We see that most of the MSME actors in the city of Palopo come from the last education of SMA/SMK/MA, so there is a lack of knowledge related to the preparation of SAK EMKM. of 1.710 with a level of sig. of 0.000. This shows that the socialization variable has a positive and significant influence on the application of SAK EMKM in the financial reports of MSMEs in Palopo City.

This is due to the existence of outreach to MSME actors about SAK EMKM Socialization is very important for MSME actors because compiling or making financial reports can increase the understanding, knowledge and skills of business actors (Susilowati et al., 2021). Socialization is also very helpful in improving the quality of financial reports for MSMEs. With socialization related to SAK EMKM, business actors are able to adapt to certain environments and become individual learning processes (Kusuma & Lutfiany, 2019). Socialization also coordinates its behavior with the behavior of others and learns in accordance with the roles and regulations that have been set related to financial accounting standards for micro, small and medium entities. This research is in line with the results of research conducted by Sutapa (2020) stated that socialization had an influence on the implementation of SAK EMKM.

The Level of Education Influences the Application of SAK EMKM

Based on the second hypothesis, it shows that the education level variable shows a positive value of 3.005 with a sig level. of 0.003. This shows

that the education level variable has a positive and significant influence on the implementation of SAK EMKM in the financial reports of Palopo City MSMEs.

According to Mutiari & Yudiantara (2021) states that there are several factors that can influence the views of MSME business actors regarding the importance of financial reports for business development, one of which is the last level of education. Having an adequate educational background can cause MSME business actors to be able to make financial reports in accordance with SAK EMKM (Febriyanti & Wardhani, 2018). According to Kusuma (2019), his research stated that the level of education influences the implementation of SAK EMKM.

Perception Influences the Application of SAK EMKM

Based on the third hypothesis, it shows that the perception variable shows a positive value of 2.696 with a sig level. of 0.000. This shows that the perception variable has a positive value that influences and is significant on the application of the EMKM SAK in the financial reports of MSMEs in Palopo City. Perception is an integrated response within the individual so that he organizes and interprets stimuli to his senses. In this case, other people's perceptions will relate to the object (Kusuma & Lutfiany, 2019). With this, a person's perception will be aware of the situation around him and also the situation in himself. This shows that with the perception of MSME actors towards SAK EMKM, MSME actors can interpret information by developing their business so that their business is better than before (Susilowati et al., 2021). The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Syukrina (2018) which states that perceptions affect the application of SAK EMKM.

Understanding of Accounting Affects the Application of SAK EMKM

Based on the fourth hypothesis, it shows that the accounting comprehension variable shows a positive value of 3.252 with a sig. of 0.002. This shows that the accounting understanding variable has a positive and significant influence on the application of SAK EMKM in the financial reports of MSMEs in Palopo City.

Understanding of accounting is a person's ability to understand knowledge of accounting science related to the process of bookkeeping and financial reporting by referring to and referring to the current financial accounting principles and standards (Mutiari & Yudiantara, 2021). Understanding of MSME business actors related to accounting is currently still lacking because it can be seen from the variable regression results that are still very low. Business actors' understanding of financial reports will support improving the quality of business financial reports (Susilowati et al., 2021). Understanding accounting is a person's ability to understand and understand something related to accounting science. Understanding means knowing something and it can be seen from various aspects, for example when someone gives an explanation and interprets a word using their own sentence (Mutiari & Yudiantara, 2021). The results of this study are in line with research conducted

by Neneng Salmiah, Satria Tri Nanda (2018) stated that understanding of accounting influences the application of SAK EMKM.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study aims to analyze and find out the factors that influence the application of SAK EMKM to MSME business actors in Palopo City. The research results and discussion that has been carried out, the following conclusions can be drawn. First based on the results of the analysis shows that socialization has an effect on the application of SAK EMKM. This shows that socialization is very important for MSMEs in preparing financial reports so that they can increase the understanding, knowledge and skills of business actors.

Second, based on the results of the analysis, it shows that the level of education influences the application of SAK EMKM. This shows that having an adequate educational background supports MSME business actors in making financial reports in accordance with SAK EMKM. Third, based on the results of the analysis, it shows that perceptions influence the application of SAK EMKM. This shows that with the perception of MSME actors towards SAK EMKM, MSME actors can interpret information by developing their business so that their business is better than before. Fourth, based on the results of the analysis, it shows that the level of education influences the application of SAK EMKM. This shows that the understanding of business actors about accounting will support the improvement of the quality of business financial reports.

FURTHER STUDY

Based on the conclusions above, the authors provide suggestions for further research, namely with the results of this study, it can be an inspiration for further research with more specific studies with the same or different themes or sub-themes. In addition, the researcher hopes that competent parties will use the same methodology in conducting further research.

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